

Response to Qualification Advice List of Issues

Bologna Biomechanical Computed Tomography (BBCT)

Invented Name:	BBCT
Active substance:	NA
Pharmaco-therapeutic group:	NA
Intended indication(s):	proximal femur fragility fractures
Applicant:	Mimesis srl (Small-Medium Enterprise)
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1. List of abbreviations

aBMD: areal Bone Mineral Density

ARF0: Absolute Risk of Fracture at the time of the CT scan

ARF5: Absolute Risk of Fracture in the five years following the CT scan

BBCT: Bologna Biomechanical Computed Tomography

CoU: Context of Use

CT: Computed Tomography

DXA: Dual X-rays Absorptiometry

EMA: European Medicine Agency

EU: European Union

FE: Finite Element

LHS: Latin Hypercube Sampling

MFS: Minimum Femoral Strength

MID: Minimal Important Difference

QA: Qualification Advice

QCT: Quantitative Computed Tomography

RCT: Randomized Clinical Trial

SAWP: Scientific Advice Working Party

SD: Standard Deviation

SRM: Standardized Response Mean

vBMD: volumetric Bone Mineral Density

2. General reply

The applicant Mimesis srl has requested a qualification advice to EMA on behalf of the In Silico World Consortium, an EU-funded project in which Mimesis is a partner. The aim of this submission is pre-competitive and aims to highlight potential issues in the regulatory qualification of drug development tools based on physics-based and physiology-based patient-specific models. Our intent is to make public all proceedings of this advice process once completed, including the briefing book, so that other practitioners in academia and industry can learn from this qualification advice.

Our long-term strategy is to develop a complete simulator of a clinical trial for new treatments against osteoporosis, which includes a physiology model, a disease progression model, and a treatment model. As a first step we proposed in our submission a tool named **Bologna Biomechanical Computed Tomography (BBCT)**, which implements a CT-based physics-based predictor of the probability of a patient's femur to fracture when a fall occurs. Our preliminary studies suggest that such model is a more accurate predictor of the femoral fracture event than the DXA-based areal Bone Mineral Density (aBMD) commonly used in the clinical practice. Our assumption is that such improved predictive accuracy (around 10% better than aBMD) could be useful in all dose-response regulatory studies where the aBMD is now used as a response variable.

We agree that our request to modify the definition of a biomarker is not important nor relevant for the primary objective of this procedure, given how the discussion has evolved so far. Still, we challenge the notion that only an observational quantification (measurement) can be a biomarker. Reality is that many biomarkers accepted by regulatory agencies are not measurements, but complex computer elaborations of measurements, much like the predictions of our BBCT computer model. While we conservatively agree with the notion that a primary outcome must be observational, as it is common practice to accept measurements as surrogate biomarkers of those outcomes, we fail to see any reason why, at least in principle, a surrogate biomarker could not also be predicted.

We understand that the only primary outcome accepted by EMA to evaluate the efficacy of antiresorptive drugs to treat osteoporosis is the incidence of bone fractures. It is our understanding that EMA accepts the use of aBMD only as a response variable in dose-response studies. Our aim is to explore if the ARF0 predicted by BBCT is a better response variable than aBMD in such studies, or more precisely, if ARF0 can be considered a response variable representative of the incidence of proximal femur fractures.

But, in broader picture, we believe it is important to continue searching for surrogates to the incidence of hip fracture. The most effective drugs available on the market show efficacy in reducing hip fractures below 60%¹. This means that four patients out of ten still fractures, despite being treated. This explains why in 2019 more than 3 million fragility hip fractures were treated in the European Union (Source: International Osteoporosis Foundation). However, in spite of a clear need for better treatments, according to *clinicaltrials.gov*, there are currently no active phase I trials for new osteoporosis treatments. In a recent interview to *Endocrine Today* Sundeep Khosla, MD, professor of medicine and physiology at Mayo Clinic, said: "Continuing to use fracture as an endpoint is essentially going to prohibit any new drugs from coming to market". Considering that not treating patients at high risk of fracture is now unethical, the only possible placebo-controlled studies are on low-risk cohorts, where they require thousands of patients followed-up for years to observe a handful of hip fractures. For these reasons, we would like to continue exploring with the EMA the possibility that, in a future, a predicted outcome similar to ARF0 (or to the ARF10 indicator we are currently developing) could play a role also in the efficacy assessment of new antiresorptive drugs.

3. Applicant's response to the list of issues

We recall that in the Briefing Book submitted the assessment of the stratification accuracy for BBCT-hip ARF0 (defined as its ability to correctly classify patients in a cohort as fractured or non-fractured), was presented with reference to two different cohorts. One was the retrospective cohort presented within the Technical Validation, while the other was the prospective one, presented for the clinical validation plan. Throughout the following responses we will address to those as the Sheffield cohort (retrospective, belonging to the technical validation) and Bologna cohort (prospective, belonging to the clinical validation).

3.1. Please discuss further the proposed CoU and unmet medical need

Applicant's position

The original CoU wording that we proposed is the following:

BBCT-hip is a methodology where a stochastic biophysics model provides an estimate of the absolute Risk of proximal femur Fracture at time zero (ARF0) of a given subject, from their height, weight, and a Quantitative Computed Tomography (QCT) scan of the hip region. This ARF0 is used as a surrogate biomarker of the primary endpoint proximal femoral fracture, in place of the measured DXA-based aBMD, multi-dose Phase II studies to evaluate the efficacy of new antiresorptive treatments where the aBMD is currently an accepted primary outcome.

We understand that EMA consider as primary outcome for efficacy of a new antiresorptive drug the reduction of number of fractures observed over a given time interval, with respect to the comparator group. However, there are intermediate decisions, for example the selection of the optimal dose (dose-response studies), where the aBMD has been accepted as a response variable. For example, in the assessment report of romosozumab (Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004465/0000), in the clinical efficacy section, two dose-ranging studies (Identifier: 20060326 and Identifier: 20101291) use aBMD as response variable. Our hypothesis is that this dose-selection studies could be significantly improved if ARF0 is used in place of aBMD. In the light of this we propose the following rewording for the CoU:

BBCT-hip is a methodology where a stochastic biophysics model provides an estimate of the Absolute Risk of proximal femur Fracture upon falling at time zero (ARF0) of a given subject, from patient-specific height, weight, and a Quantitative Computed Tomography (QCT) scan of the hip region. This ARF0 is to be used as a response variable in multi-dose Phase II studies in place of the measured DXA-based aBMD. The average change in ARF0 over the period of treatment for all subjects treated with a given dose (Ave_ΔARF0) can be used as response variable, by assuming the optimal dose among those tested is the one for which Ave_ΔARF0 is most positive (or least negative).

Originally, before the preparatory meeting, we proposed that ARF0 could be used as a surrogate of the fracture endpoint; because of this, the ASME VV-40 risk analysis we conducted considered the model influence high and the model consequence high, which would demand the most severe validation plan.

ASME VV-40 risk analysis was later reviewed based on the changes in the final CoU proposed in the Qualification Advice (QA) request that we submitted. Here, in light of the above re-worded CoU and of your comments in the list of Issues document, we also rediscuss the VV-40 risk analysis. For this revised CoU, we propose that:

- **Model influence is considered high** for BBCT-hip: the ARF0 predicted by BBCT-hip is proposed as response variable in dose-response studies, in alternative of aBMD. According to this context of use the choice of optimal dose would be based entirely based on the BBCT-hip prediction.
- **Model consequence is considered low:** the dose selected is in any case lower than the maximum tolerable dose, and higher than the minimum effective dose, so an inaccurate decision would not expose the patient to any additional risk, but only to a somehow reduced efficacy.

3.2. Present an example of using ARF0 in a phase 2 clinical trial for a new osteoporosis treatment

Applicant's position

In the following, as an example, we will briefly summarize two Phase II clinical trials which were mentioned in the CHMP assessment reports for Prolia (denosumab) and Evenity (romosozumab). In those, lumbar spine BMD was adopted as primary response variable, and its percent change from baseline at month 12 evaluated as primary outcome. To follow, based on those, a possible Phase II clinical trial involving the use of ARF0 as primary response variable is presented.

Efficacy, Safety and Tolerability of Romosozumab in the Treatment of Japanese Women With Postmenopausal Osteoporosis - ClinicalTrials.gov Identifier: NCT01992159

- Inclusion criteria:
 - o postmenopausal Japanese women, aged 55–85 years
 - o dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DXA) BMD T-score of ≤ -2.5 at the lumbar spine, total hip, or femoral neck.
 - Key exclusion criteria:
 - o BMD T-score of ≤ -4.0 at the lumbar spine
 - o BMD T-score of ≤ -3.5 at the total hip or femoral neck
 - o history of vertebral or hip fracture
 - o recent use of medication affecting bone metabolism
 - o history of metabolic or bone disease (other than osteoporosis)
 - o 25-(OH) vitamin D levels < 20 ng/mL, or current hypercalcemia or hypocalcaemia.
 - Enrolled participants were randomized equally (1:1:1:1) to one of four treatment groups: placebo or romosozumab 70, 140, or 210 mg by subcutaneous (SC) injection QM for 12 months.
 - Primary efficacy endpoint:
 - o percentage change from baseline at 12 months in lumbar spine BMD by DXA scan.
- A repeated-measures model was fit with baseline BMD, machine type, interaction of baseline BMD and machine type, visit (categorical), treatment (categorical), and interaction of treatment and visit as the independent variables. Least squares mean BMD change, one-sided 95% confidence intervals (CIs) and p-values were presented for pairwise comparisons between each of the romosozumab treatment groups and placebo and adjusted for multiplicity.
- Secondary efficacy endpoints:
 - o percentage change from baseline at 6 months in lumbar spine BMD
 - o percentage change from baseline at 6 and 12 months in total hip and femoral neck BMD
 - o bone turnover markers P1NP and CTX
 - o safety endpoints were patient incidences of adverse events, changes from baseline in laboratory assessments (fasting blood samples at baseline, week 1, and months 1, 2, 3, 6, 9, and 12), and patient incidences of anti-romosozumab antibodies (at baseline and months 1, 3, 6, 9, 12, and 15).

Statistical methods similar to those for the primary endpoint were used for analysis of secondary BMD endpoints but without adjustment for multiple comparisons. Bone turnover markers were summarized graphically, and the Wilcoxon rank sum test was used to assess pairwise differences between each of the treatment groups and placebo at each time point without adjustment for multiplicity.

Determine the Efficacy, Safety and Tolerability of Denosumab (AMG 162) in the Treatment of Postmenopausal Women With Low Bone Mineral Density - ClinicalTrials.gov Identifier: NCT00043186

This randomized, placebo-controlled, dose-ranging study included eight double-blind groups and one open-label treatment group.

- Inclusion criteria:

- postmenopausal women up to 80 years of age with T score of -1.8 to -4.0 at the lumbar spine or -1.8 to -3.5 at either the femoral neck or total hip.
- Exclusion criteria:
 - use of bisphosphonates within the previous 12 months or fluoride within the previous 24 months
 - tibolone, parathyroid hormone or any derivative, systemic glucocorticoids, inhaled glucocorticoids, anabolic steroids or testosterone within 6 months
 - oestrogens, selective estrogenic receptor modulators, calcitonin, or calcitriol within 3 months before enrolment
 - hyperparathyroidism or hypoparathyroidism, hyperthyroidism or hypothyroidism, hypocalcemia, rheumatoid arthritis
 - Paget's disease of bone, osteomalacia, a creatinine clearance of less than 35 ml per minute (as estimated by the Cockcroft–Gault equation),¹¹ malabsorption syndrome, a recent long-bone fracture (within the previous six months), more than one grade 1 vertebral fracture, an osteoporosis-related fracture within the previous two years, or a case in which bone mineral density could not be accurately measured.
- A total of 412 women from 29 study centres in the United States were randomly assigned to receive denosumab given subcutaneously either every three months (at a dose of 6, 14, or 30 mg) or every six months (at a dose of 14, 60, 100, or 210 mg), open-label alendronate (at a dose of 70 mg) given orally once weekly, or placebo. The randomization was stratified according to centre with permuted blocks of eight. All subjects took daily oral supplements containing elemental calcium (1 g) and vitamin D (400 IU). Institutional review boards at each study site approved the study protocol, and all subjects provided written informed consent.
- Primary efficacy end point:
 - percentage change in BMD at the lumbar spine

Measurements of bone mineral density of the lumbar spine were performed by dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry (GE Lunar or Hologic) at baseline and at 1, 3, 6, and 12 months. The mean percentage changes from baseline in bone mineral density and markers of bone turnover were determined by analysis of covariance models, with treatment as the main effect and the location of the centre and the baseline value of the end point as covariates. For the primary assessment, pairwise comparisons between each group receiving denosumab and the placebo group were conducted for each efficacy measure, and the levels of significance were adjusted for multiple testing with the use of the Hochberg procedure.

- Secondary efficacy end points:
 - Percentage changes from baseline in BMD at the total hip, femoral neck at 1, 3, 6, and 12 months, total body (minus head), and distal third of the radius
 - serum levels of C-telopeptide, the urinary N-telopeptide: creatinine ratio, and bone-specific alkaline phosphatase.

Measurements of bone mineral density of the total hip, and femoral neck were performed by dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry (GE Lunar or Hologic) at baseline and at 1, 3, 6, and 12 months and of the distal third of the radius and total body at baseline and at 6 and 12 months. Urine N-telopeptide (Osteomark) in fasting samples were measured at baseline, at 3 days, and monthly through 12 months, with an additional measurement 3 days after the 6-month visit. Bone-specific alkaline phosphatase (Tandem-R Ostase, Hybritech, or Access Ostase, Beckman Coulter) and intact parathyroid hormone (Nichols) were assessed at baseline and at months 1, 3, 6, 9 (bone-specific alkaline phosphatase only), and 12. Hematologic and chemical analyses and serum levels of denosumab and denosumab-binding antibodies were recorded at all study visits. Reports of adverse events were collected spontaneously and in response to nondirected questioning at each study visit.

An example of using ARFO in a phase 2 clinical trial for a new osteoporosis treatment

- Inclusion criteria:
 - o ambulatory postmenopausal women, aged 55–85 years.
 - o T-score of eligible patients from –1.0 to –3.5 at either the femoral neck or total hip. An upper limit of –1.0 is selected to include subjects with both osteopenia and osteoporosis.
- Exclusion criteria:
 - o T-score of ≤ -3.5 at the total hip or femoral neck, or a history of vertebral or hip fracture, history of metabolic or bone disease (other than osteoporosis).
- Based on the treatment to be tested, enrolled participants are randomized equally to one of the identified treatment groups: placebo or treatment $d_1, d_2, d_3, \dots, d_n$ mg (where the generic d_i refers to the i^{th} dose to be tested, n to the total number of doses) administered for 12 months. Dosing adjustments for the assigned study treatment are not permitted. Depending on the treatment being tested, patients in each treatment group might receive daily supplementation with calcium and vitamin D. If required by the treatment, after the 12-month treatment period patients might be followed for another 3 months for assessment of anti-treatment antibody formation.
- All study personnel and patients are blinded to the treatment assignment. All patients provide informed written consent to participate. The study is conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. An investigational review board approves the study design for each centre.
- Primary efficacy endpoint:
 - o change from baseline at 12 months in ARFO.

CT scans are performed at screening and at month 12. The mean percentage change from baseline in ARFO is determined by analysis of covariance models, with treatment as the main effect and the baseline value of the end point as covariates. For the primary assessment, pairwise comparisons between each group receiving treatment and the placebo group are conducted for each efficacy measure, and the levels of significance were adjusted for multiple testing.

- Secondary efficacy endpoints:
 - o bone turnover markers measured at each time point
 - o Safety endpoints considered are patient incidences of adverse events, changes from baseline in laboratory assessments, and patient incidences of antibodies. Study visits include screening, baseline, week 1, monthly visits in months 1–12, and month 15. Adverse events are recorded at all visits.
 - o If required, assessments of antibodies occur at baseline and months 1, 3, 6, 9, 12, and 15. Fasting blood samples are analysed at baseline, week 1, and months 1, 2, 3, 6, 9, and 12. Reports of adverse events are collected spontaneously and in response to nondirected questioning at each study visit.

Overall, the study will be powered so as to detect significant effects on each variable. An expected mean difference in ARFO between active and control groups will be predetermined.

3.3. Discuss the construct validity of ARFO

Applicant's position

Contrary to QFracture or FRAX, the ARFO predicted by BBCT-Hip is not a statistical predictor. The goal in building BBCT-hip is not to build a phenomenological predictor using all quantities that are known to correlate with what we want to predict. Our goal is to build a mechanistic predictor that use reliable biophysics knowledge to model the biomechanics of the fall and bone fracture events as informed by a small number of measurements (CT scan, height, weight); all the other factors listed above (gender, age, ethnicity, family history, lack of physical activity, body frame size, etc.; alcohol consumption, vision problems, dementia, etc.) are considered in our predictive model as inter-subject variability. However, various studies published so far suggest that CT scan, height, and weight, when used to inform a biophysical model like BBCT-hip, can explain 85% of the inter-subject variability.

In the briefing book we probably were not sufficiently clear, and we apologise for this. As already mentioned elsewhere, BBCT-hip is composed of two different sub-models: on one hand a mathematical model which produces possible impact forces caused by a fall on the side and the fraction of such force transferred to the femur, on the other hand a finite element model of the patient-specific femur, only based on QCT data which allows to assess the strength, i.e. the load causing the femur fracture. Considering multiple femur orientations (impact poses) during the impact, multiple strength values can be calculated, and the Minimum Femoral Strength (MFS) computed. Hence, the MFS only depends on the femur geometry and densitometric information provided by the QCT images. ARFO instead is the result of the comparison between the calculated possible impact forces and the load on the femur which would cause its fracture (strength), which allows to compute, among the million computed impact forces, which will cause a fracture. We would expect MFS to be correlated to the age of the patient, and ARFO to be correlated to the height.

Contrary to what we wrote in the briefing book, clearly no single variable should be strongly correlated to MSF or ARFO, because if that was true the usefulness of BBCT-Hip would be questionable. For example, in the Sheffield cohort, ARFO shows a stratification accuracy of 85.2%, whereas the patient's age has an accuracy near to 50% (which is the same of tossing a coin). However, following the biophysical theory behind the model we would expect the MFS to be weakly but significantly correlated with age, since the bone mineral density (prime determinant of MFS together with anatomy) is known to decrease with age. Similarly, ARFO would be expected to show a weak but significant correlation with height. If such weak correlation were found, we propose this would demonstrate **convergent validity**. On the other hand, we proposed that **discriminant validity** could be demonstrated if MFS does not correlate with height and weight. However, upon reflection, this may not be the case. Thus, we propose to evaluate the discriminant validity by showing the ARFO does not correlate with heart rate at rest, systolic blood pressure, postal code of residence, and socioeconomic status as assessed with a validated questionnaire such as the National Statistics Socio-economic Classification, known not to be correlated with and increased fracture incidence.

3.4. Taking into account the comments in the scientific discussion propose an alternative clinical validation plan to address both the predictive capacity and sensitivity to change

Applicant's position

Thank you for these comments; we believe this is the most important topic of this qualification advice. We accept your criticisms on the design and the sample size of clinical validation study we originally proposed. We will propose here below two possible alternative designs for a clinical study aimed to demonstrate the validity of ARFO as response variable.

The conundrum we face is this: on one hand the comparison with aBMD follows a more traditional approach where a new response variable is validated by comparing it to an accepted one. On the other hand, we expect a clinical study based only on ARFO to be powered with a number of patients lower than that of aBMD, so if we could limit the study to ARFO, the complexity of the study would be reduced (we could still include aBMD but power the study for ARFO). This is true considering that aBMD is related to the risk of hip fracture by an unknown, non-linear function. Therefore, the accuracy of using aBMD to predict the risk of hip fracture varies considerably between sub-populations; thus, it is necessary to enrol a large number of patients in the validation study. In light of this we propose two possible designs, on which we ask SAWP comments:

Design #1

In the CoU we considered the DXA-aBMD is accepted as response variable in escalating dose studies. Our hypothesis is that our CT-based ARFO would be a better response variable than DXA-based aBMD for such studies.

The role of a response variable is similar to that of a surrogate biomarker, in the sense that, given an accepted clinical outcome (the fracture incidence in this case), the response variable provides an estimate of how such outcome would change due to the dose, while being easier to measure (e. g. cheaper, less invasive, or simply available in a shorter time) than the outcome itself; thus, a good response variable is a good surrogate of the outcome. If this is true, ARFO is "better" than aBMD if, it can be shown it discriminate between doses significantly better than aBMD.

The clinical validation we propose is the following:

- We enrol a group of naïf patients (who were never treated for osteoporosis before) in a randomised double-blind interventional clinical trial with inclusion and exclusion criteria that reproduce in the cohort the heterogeneity of the target population. In particular, as a good treatment is expected to reduce the risk of fracture in both osteopenic and osteoporotic patients, we would enrol patients with a wide range of T-score, including those with a very low one.
- We randomly treat them with an approved second-line treatment or with a comparator, typically bisphosphonates (we suspect it would be difficult to obtain ethical approval for a study where we do not treat patients with low bone density); the second-line treatment should have already showed in phase III clinical studies that it can reduce the incidence of hip fracture compared to a group treated with bisphosphonates.
- At outset we examine each patient with DXA and with QCT. We repeat after 12 months of treatment.
- We collect the clinical information required to calculate FRAX, QFracture and Garvan risk factors; we use QCT to calculate vBMD.
- We exclude from the study patients who fracture the hip in the first 12 months of the study.
- We follow-up with controls every 12 months each patient in the two groups for up to 5 years or until the hip fracture occurs, we record the fracture event and the time to fracture.

ARFO validation will be based on the following evidence:

- **Construct validity**
 - o *Convergent validity*: the correlation between MFS and age and the correlation between ARFO and height will be tested (see reply to Issue 3.3). We will also test the correlation between aBMD and MFS.

- *Known groups:* 1) at baseline compare ARFO between osteoporotic/osteopenic groups; while the risk of fracture of these two groups is known to overlap, ARFO of osteoporotic patients should be higher than that of osteopenic patients. 2) Compare ARFO at baseline with that after 12 months of treatment; ARFO should be reduced, since we know the treatment is effective.
- *Discriminant validity:* The correlation between ARFO and variables known not be correlated with the construct will be tested: heart rate at rest, systolic blood pressure, postal code of residence, and socioeconomic status (see reply to Issue 3.3)
- **Predictive capacity**
Our hypothesis is that at the end of the study the ARFO calculated after 12 months of treatment, when used to separate the fractured and non-fractured patients, will show a number of false positives and of false negatives lower than that of the aBMD measured at the same time point. We also assume that the stratification accuracy of ARFO is better than that provided by FRAX, QFracture, Garvan, or vBMD alone.
- **The ability to detect change**
 - *Longitudinal validity:* we will test the change in ARFO between t=0 and t=12m (Δ ARFO) shows a longitudinal correlation with respect to the time to fracture which is better than that of the change in aBMD (Δ aBMD);
 - *MID:* the verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification of the BBCT patient-specific model indicates a predictive accuracy (which accounts for epistemic, aleatoric, and numerical errors) of 15% for the force to fracture of cadaver femurs, with the numerical error well below 5% and the aleatoric error due to the uncertainty of the model's inputs never exceed 8%. This value coincides with the stratification accuracy of ARFO for the Sheffield cohort. Thus, we propose that the minimal clinically important difference for ARFO is 15%.
 - *Responsiveness:* our hypothesis is that Δ ARFO discriminates the two treatments with a level of statistical significance higher than Δ aBMD. Before opening the labels which identify the patients as belonging to one of the two treatment group, we will analyse the probability distribution of Δ ARFO and of Δ aBMD and confirm that they are bimodal. Using clustering methods for bimodal distributions we will infer from both Δ ARFO and Δ aBMD which cases were treated with the treatment and which with the comparator. Once the labels are open, the accuracy of this classification should be higher for Δ ARFO than for Δ aBMD. Once the labels are open, we re-cluster the values of Δ ARFO and Δ aBMD for type of treatment; our hypothesis is that the difference between the average Δ ARFO for the two treatment groups should have a statistical significance higher than that for Δ aBMD. Once the labels are open, we will compute the Standardized Response Mean (SRM) for Δ ARFO for the two treatment groups and compare it with that of Δ aBMD. We expect the SRM in the treatment group to be higher for Δ ARFO than for Δ aBMD. We also expect the difference between the SRM computed on Δ ARFO for the two treatment groups to have a statistical significance higher than that for Δ aBMD.

With respect to the numerosity, given the study is powered for Δ aBMD, for which ample literature is available, once selected the treatment to be tested and the comparator, we will extract from literature an estimate of the average and variance and use it to power the study appropriately.

Design #2

We revise the CoU to remove any reference to the aBMD, and we propose ARFO as response variable in escalating dose studies. Our hypothesis is that ARFO could be used as proxy for efficacy (measured by the outcome reduction of the number of hip fractures with respect to comparator). We validate this hypothesis by comparing the dose-response using the hip fracture outcome, and the ARFO response variable.

The clinical validation we propose is the following:

- We enrol a group of naïf patients (who were never treated for osteoporosis before) in a randomised double-blind interventional clinical trial with inclusion and exclusion criteria that reproduce in the cohort the heterogeneity of the target population. In particular, as a good treatment is expected to reduce the risk of fracture in both osteopenic and osteoporotic patients, we would enrol patients with a wide range of T-score, including those with a very low one.
- We randomly treat them with two different doses of an approved treatment; the two doses will be chosen looking at published dose-response studies for that drug; the difference between the two doses is selected looking at the smallest difference that was found detectable by whatever response variable was used in the published studies.
- At outset we examine each patient with QCT. We repeat after 12 months of treatment.
- We collect the clinical information (including DXA-aBMD) required to calculate FRAX, QFracture and Garvan risk factors; we use QCT to calculate vBMD.
- We exclude from the study patients who fracture the hip in the first 12 months of the study.
- We follow-up with controls every 12 months each patient in the two groups for up to 5 years or until the hip fracture occurs, we record the fracture event and the time to fracture.

ARFO validation will be based on the following evidence:

- **Construct validity**
 - *Convergent validity*: the correlation between MFS and age and the correlation between ARFO and height will be tested (see reply to Issue 3.3). We will also test the correlation between aBMD and MFS.
 - *Known groups*: 1) at baseline compare ARFO between osteoporotic/osteopenic groups; while the risk of fracture of these two groups is known to overlap, ARFO of osteoporotic patients should be higher than that of osteopenic patients. 2) Compare ARFO at baseline with that after 12 months of treatment; ARFO should be reduced, since we know the treatment is effective.
 - *Discriminant validity*: The correlation between ARFO and variables known not be correlated with the construct will be tested: heart rate at rest, systolic blood pressure, postal code of residence, and socioeconomic status (see reply to Issue 3.3)
- **Predictive capacity**

Our hypothesis is that at the end of the study the ARFO calculated after 12m of treatment, when used to separate the fractured and non-fractured patients, will show a low number of false positives and of false negatives.
- **The ability to detect change** can be validated if we can demonstrate:
 - *Longitudinal validity*: the change in ARFO between $t=0$ and $t=12m$ ($\Delta ARFO$) shows a longitudinal correlation with respect to the time to hip fracture.
 - *MID*: the verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification of the BBCT patient-specific model indicates a predictive accuracy (which accounts for epistemic, aleatoric, and numerical errors) of 15% for the force to fracture of cadaver femurs, with the numerical error well below 5% and the aleatoric error due to the uncertainty of the model's inputs never exceed 8%. This value coincides with the stratification accuracy of ARFO for the Sheffield cohort. Thus, we propose that the minimal clinically important difference for ARFO is 15%.
 - *Responsiveness*: our hypothesis is that $\Delta ARFO$ discriminates the two treatment doses with a level of statistical significance sufficient to be used as response variable, and comparable to that obtained using the fracture outcome. Before opening the labels, we will analyse the probability distribution of $\Delta ARFO$ and confirm that it is bimodal. Using clustering methods for bimodal distributions we will infer which cases were treated with the low dose and which with the high dose. Once the labels are open, the accuracy of this classification should be good.

Once the labels are open, we re-cluster the values of ΔARF0 for treatment dose; the hypothesis is that the difference between the mean ΔARF0 of the two treatment groups is statistically significant.

With respect to the numerosity, we propose to use an adaptive design; we will initially enrol 50 patients for each dose group; after the second CT control at 12 months, we will decompose the bimodal distribution of ΔARF0 into two monomodal distributions using clustering methods for bimodal distributions and calculate the statistical power of probability that the two monomodal distributions are different. The hypotheses we make are that clustering obtained assuming the distribution of ΔARF0 bimodal is a good approximation of that obtained with the label information. If with 50 patients per group the test is not powered at least at 80%, we enrol another 50 patients per group, and after 12 months we will repeat the power analysis. The power analysis will be repeated using the actual labels to cluster the value for each group of patients once they have completed their five years follow-up.

The reason why in this second case we propose an adaptive design is that we are not so convinced that a very large number of patients is necessary to demonstrate responsiveness in this case. aBMD is related to the risk of hip fracture by an unknown, non-linear function. As such is it possible (as in fact it is) that the accuracy of using aBMD to predict the risk of hip fracture varies considerably between sub-populations; thus, it is necessary to enrol a large number of patients in the validation study. But the relation of ΔARF0 to the risk of hip fracture is mostly mechanistic; the only non-deterministic part of the fall and fracture event are the initial kinematics conditions of the fall, and the postural attenuation, which are accounted for stochastically. We believe this is an important difference. Our hypothesis, which has been confirmed in all the technical validation of cadaver bones, is that the prediction error affecting the ΔARF0 does not change significantly between subjects. The smoothness of the prediction error as the inputs vary is an implicit assumption of the Applicability Analysis described in the ASME V&V-40. Of course, all this needs to be demonstrated, which is why we propose an adaptive design.

We hope that at least one of these two designs for the clinical validation study will be considered acceptable by the panel experts. However, we would like to add a more general reflection. Originally, we proposed a more ambitious context of use, were ARF0 was proposed as a surrogate of the fracture endpoint. Based on that we proposed that the validation plan had to be the most rigorous, considering that the risk analysis based on the VV-40 gave us high model influence and high model consequence. As a result of the discussion with the SAWP, the revised context of use suggests using ARF0 only as a response variable for dose-response studies. Accordingly, in our reply to issue 3.1 we proposed a revised risk analysis, where the model consequence is considered low. Now, coherently one would expect the level of evidence of the validation plan should also become lower. On the contrary, the two possible revisions of the clinical validation plan we proposed above (revised following the suggestions of the SAWP), settle at a considerably higher level of evidence.

To be fair, in the list of issues it is mentioned the use of existing registries as an option for clinical validation. However, as for most similar models, this is not a viable option. The clinical research protocols that inform all clinical registries of this kind do not include the data required as input for BBCT-hip. The clinical validation we propose, based on the HipOp collection, was the closest dataset we could find. These are 4000 calibrated CT scans collected for surgical planning purposes. However, most cases do have anatomical deformities or a previous metallic implant already present, which creates artefacts; once these are excluded 200-300 cases in the best case remain. The real problem is that very few patients among those 200-300 experienced a femoral neck fracture within five years from the CT scan. If we consider the stratification error analysis as the power of the area under the curve depends on the balance between positive and negative events, a power analysis of the HipOp collection suggests more than 700 cases would be required with a 1:25 ratio between fractured and non-fractured patients. The only alternative is to use a balanced cohort like the Sheffield collection we used for the technical validation. There, since fractured cases as 50% of the total, 100 cases are enough to

power the AUC analysis. However, this involves scanning patients after they fracture, so the observation is retrospective.

3.5. Please discuss the performance of the proposed new tool as compared to aBMD and other available prognostic and surrogate biomarkers for treatment efficacy in osteoporosis. It is unclear how much better prediction of fractures the model will produce compared to only a QCT-scan. The Applicant should compare their methodology to the conclusions based on the QCT-scan (which produces the vBMD-measure). Please also discuss the available data that support the use of ARF0 as a prediction model compared to aBMD and other available prediction tools

Applicant's position

In the revised design #1 for the clinical validation study we proposed, (see reply to issue 3.4) we added that in terms of stratification accuracy ARF0 should prove to be better than aBMD, but also better than FRAX, QFracture, Garvan, and using vBMD alone. We expect this to be the case.

For example, in the Sheffield cohort, the stratification accuracy of ARF0 is 85%, that of aBMD is 75%, while that of Sheffield-own FRAX is 69%, and the vBMD (total hip) is 75.2%²

3.6. Please discuss the sensitivity of the output of BBCT-hip with respect to the annual falling rate

Applicant's position

First of all, we would like to highlight an important point which is also connected with the reply to your issue n. 8 (3.8). The future we envision for BBCT-hip methodology will involve an evolution of the in silico methodology presented in the context of this qualification advice request. In fact, we are currently developing an additional model able to reproduce the progression of the disease (i.e. the progressive bone loss) in parallel to a model which will be able to reproduce the effect of specific treatments (e.g. bisphosphonates) on bone density. When these are fully developed, it will be possible to integrate them within the herein presented BBCT-hip methodology. Therefore, it will be possible, starting from a QCT at time t_0 (i.e. time of the QCT), to predict the risk of fracture for a naïf patient in the following 1, 5 or 10 years. In such simulation, the fall rate will have to be considered, as 95% of the hip fracture occurring worldwide are known to be caused by a fall. In addition, we will also be able to include the treatment model, which will allow us to predict the risk of fracture at e.g. 1, 5, 10 years for patients administered with a treatment.

For the time being, however, and in the context of this submission, we are only dealing with ARF0, i.e. the absolute risk of fracture upon falling at time 0 (i.e. the time of the CT scan). The choice to include the fall rate in ARF0 definition was dictated by the future steps we were envisioning. Nevertheless, that was not strictly necessary, and following your comments we concluded ARF0 could have simply been defined as P , defined as the ratio between the number of simulated falls for which the model predicts fracture, and the total number of simulated falls (see reply to issue n. 18 (3.18) for details).

However, for the sake of completeness, in Fig. 3.6.1 below you can see that the relationship between P and ARF0 (Equation 1) as the annual probability of falling, n , varies. In the case $n=1$, $ARF0=P$. If $n=0$, i.e. no falls occur, ARF0 will be 0, because ARF0 is the probability of fracturing upon falling. For any other value of n , as shown, ARF0 is a monotonic function of P , and a bijective correspondence exists between them. This means that the stratification accuracy of ARF0 will not change no matter the value of n that is used.

$$ARF0 = 1 - (1 - P)^n \quad (1)$$

Figure 3.6.1 ARF0 variation as a function of P for different n values. P values come from the Sheffield cohort related outcomes.

Moreover, as shown in Fig. 3.6.2, the ROC curve remains unchanged if either ARF0 or P are used as predictors. Of course, the threshold identified on the ROC curve by maximising precision will change based on the considered predictor, but that will not affect the overall stratification accuracy once either P or ARF0 are chosen consistently.

Figure 3.6.2 Comparison between the ROC curves obtained by using ARF0 and P respectively as predictors of the fracture status for the Sheffield cohort.

3.7. Please justify the relevance of the deterministic and stochastic parameters values used in the fall mathematical model for the proposed CoU

Applicant's position

BBCT-hip employs a mathematical mechanistic model to estimate the impact force at the femur for a person who is falling in a determined way. But falling is not a deterministic event, as one person might fall in a number of different ways. Therefore, basically all the non-strictly patient-specific parameters involved in the equations for the force definition are treated as stochastic variables.

For each stochastic variable we provide a frequency distribution that is sampled. Such distributions were generated in two ways: for some, the min-max values were derived in large part from biophysics consideration, and the normality of the distribution over such range was postulated. For others, the range of values were measured experimentally and reported in one or more cited publications.

In the following, we detail for each stochastic variable, justification and relevance for the adopted min-max values.

- **Initial fall angle θ_i**

In order to define the lowest and highest possible initial inclination body at the start of the fall, reference was made to:

- The observational study of Robinovitch and coworkers³, where digital video cameras were installed in common areas in two long-term care facilities in British Columbia, Canada to capture falls and their causes. Residents in the two facilities had a mean age of 81 years (± 12) and 82 years (± 10) respectively. Of the 130 individuals with captured falls, mean age was 78 years (± 10), and 52% were women. It was found that the most common activity at the time of a fall was walking forward, which accounted for 24% (54 of 227) of falls. Three other activities were also commonly associated with falls: standing quietly, sitting down or lowering, and initiation of walking. Hence, the lowest possible angle was fixed at 0° , corresponding to a standing position. Negative values would have been unphysical.
- Experimental works by⁴⁻⁶ where subjects were released from forward leans and instructed to regain standing balance by taking a single step forward. The aim was the identification of the maximum forward lean angle from which, upon sudden release, subjects could recover balance using a single rapid step. In⁶ twenty-one volunteers participated, 10 males and 11 females. The average age was 26.8 and 28.4 years old, with a range of 18–33 and 21–36 years old for males and females, respectively. There, an average equivalent disturbance angle of $14.9 \pm 4.4^\circ$ was found. In⁵ instead, ten young (mean age 25.0 years) and 10 older (73.7 years) healthy women were enrolled. Five of the 10 older women could not recover balance with a single step after release from the smallest of the imposed forward leans. For the 5 older women who succeeded in recovering as instructed from at least one lean, the mean maximum lean angle was significantly smaller than that for young women (16.2° vs 30.7° , $p < .001$). In⁴ eventually, ten young (mean age 24.3 years) and ten old (72.8 years) healthy males took part in the experiments. The calculated mean equivalent lean angles corresponding to the imposed lean control cable loads ranged from 13.3 to 30.0° among the old and 13.5 to 43.0° among the young.

Given the results of the above-mentioned studies, where elderly individuals with the exception of⁶ were included, the upper limit for the angle θ_i was set to 30° .

- **Final fall angle θ_f**

To assess the angle of the body with respect to the vertical at the end of the fall event it was necessary to identify the most common activities prior to a fall. Therefore, the descriptive study of Talbot and coworkers was referenced⁷, where participants completed a fall history questionnaire describing the circumstances surrounding falls in the previous two years. Three different age groups were investigated,

a young age group (20–45 years) including 292 participants, a middle-aged group (46–65 years) with 616 participants and an older aged group (> 65 years) including 589 participants. The most frequent fall causes in all gender and age groups were identified as ambulation and transferring (including getting in/out of bed, chair, wheelchair, or car, getting on/off toilet, climbing stool, chair, or ladder, and falling off stool or chair). Moreover, in the study, the environmental factor contributing to the highest percentage of falls was uneven surfaces/steps. In older fallers, the majority of falls occurred while walking on a level surface during ordinary daily activities in the absence of hazardous behaviour. Therefore, the angle (with respect to the vertical) at impact was sampled between a minimum value of 60°, accounting for the possibility of falling while climbing stairs, and 120°, which may be representative of either a fall during stairs descent or a fall from a stool. The average pitch angle, i.e. the average inclination of a step with respect to the horizontal, was set to 30°, and a similar result was obtained for a stool with 44 cm average height.

- **Initial velocity**

Since among the activities associated to the occurrence of a fall³ standing quietly was mentioned, the lowest truncation value for the initial velocity of the fall was set to 0 m/s. On the other hand, the highest truncation value was set to the highest walking speed identified in a group of individuals aged 60-69 years. This value was identified in an experimental study⁸ including 100 healthy subjects (50 males, 50 females), with 10 males and 10 females for each decade between the ages of 20 and 69, where walking speed was identified by measuring trunk acceleration of the participants during a 5-min treadmill session using a 3D accelerometer. A velocity equal to 1.4 m/s was identified as the highest value reported for the 60-69 years group and was used as upper truncation value.

- **Initial acceleration**

In accordance with the afore-mentioned results of Robinovitch and coworkers³, and coherently with the condition of standing still prior to a fall, the lowest limit was set to 0 m/s². As for the highest limit, the vertical COM acceleration corresponding to the most accelerated phase of gait was considered. To find it, reference was made to⁹, where whole body kinematics and ground reactions were recorded for 21 healthy young (21–32 y) and 20 healthy older adults (66–81 y) walking at 80%, 100% and 120% of preferred speed along a 10 m walkway⁹. The acceleration values corresponding to the older group were considered and a vertical COM acceleration value of 5.1 m/s² was reported.

- **Postural reflex attenuation coefficient η_p**

It is known that impact velocity and kinetic energy are reduced by energy absorption events, such as the ability to absorb energy in the lower extremity muscles during the descent phase of the fall. Hence, for assessing the truncation values for the distribution of the η_p coefficient reference was made to¹⁰. In this study, the effect of energy absorption by the lower extremity muscles during the descent phase of the fall was investigated. In particular, the theoretical effect on fall severity of lower extremity muscle contractions during descent (i. e. attempting to raise the link above the joint) was studied through a two-dimensional three-links inverted pendulum model of a fall. The model incorporated ideal torque generators to simulate the net effect of bilateral contraction of the muscles spanning the ankles, knees, and hips, which affected the impact configuration of the body (e. g. the trunk in an upright configuration, or knee extension during the final stage of descent). The effect of a varying degree of muscle activation on impact severity was determined by conducting simulations with different “strength factors” applied to each joint, ranging from 20 to 100 percent of peak attainable values measured in young healthy females under isometric conditions. It was found that, compared to the kinetic energy developed by a one link model with zero ankle torque, the above-mentioned strength factors could produce a 50 to 80 % attenuation of the vertical kinetic energy, and were therefore adopted as truncation parameters of the distribution. We are aware the peak torque values were obtained for young healthy female subjects, but we were forced to use those due to scarcity of these data in the literature.

- **Attenuation coefficients due to floor material η_I^{floor}**

In order to set the truncation values for η_I^{floor} , reference was made to the study of Laing and Robinovitch¹¹. In their work, a hip impact simulator able to measure the force delivered to the femoral neck during a simulated sideways fall was employed to assess the femoral neck force for four energy-absorbing floors compared to a rigid floor. The system consisted of an impact pendulum and surrogate pelvis, released by an electromagnet from a raised position and striking the ground horizontally. The surrogate pelvis was made of simulated soft tissues and an artificial proximal femur. The soft tissues were built using foams and their stiffness matched to within one SD the values measured from elderly women at nine pelvic locations surrounding the greater trochanter. The highest attenuation factor identified was 87%: the truncation values for this parameter were therefore set to 0 (rigid floor) and 0.87.

- **Attenuation coefficients due to hip protectors η_I^{ext}**

Reference was made to a study following the one cited above, where the same hip impact simulator was used to measure the attenuation in peak femoral neck force provided by two commercially available soft shell protectors against a rigid shell protector¹². The surrogate pelvis was characterized by geometry and soft tissue stiffness as measured in 15 elderly women (mean age of 77.5 years). The highest force attenuation was achieved during a low velocity fall and was 33.8%. Therefore, the truncation values were set to 0 (no protector) and 0.338.

- **Attenuation coefficients due to active soft tissue damping η_I^{act}**

In order to define truncation values for the coefficient accounting for the role of contracted muscles at impact the experiments performed in¹³ were referenced, where seven males and seven females ranging in age from 20 to 35 years and in bodyweight from 489 to 916 N underwent lateral pelvis release experiments. Prior to brake release, each subject was instructed either to completely relax the body (muscle-relaxed) or contract the trunk and back muscles in an attempt to raise the head and shoulder off the shoulder support (muscle-active). Each subject underwent five muscle-relaxed and five muscle-active pelvis release measures at six predetermined end loads. It was found that the muscle-active configuration caused an increase in the peak impact force. Therefore, truncation values ranging from 0 to -2.55 were used to include the amplifying effect of muscle contraction at the impact.

3.8. Please clarify how output of BBCT-hip predictions should be interpreted and why you choose this presented normalisation approach

Applicant's position

The original definition of ARFO was $ARFO = 1 - (1 - P)^n$, according to the binomial theorem.

Binomial probability refers to the probability of exactly x successes on n repeated trials in an experiment which has two possible outcomes (commonly called a binomial experiment). We considered each trial as a fall occurring 0.65 times (fall rate over a year). We considered P (the probability of fracture) as the probability of success, $1 - P$ (the probability of no fracture) as the probability of failure.

The binomial probability is given by $\binom{n}{x} P^x \cdot (1 - P)^{n-x}$. This means that by setting $x = 0$ there will be 0 successes (i.e. fractures) over n trials, which hence gives the probability of not fracturing over n falls: $1 \cdot (1 - P)^n = (1 - P)^n$. It follows that the probability of fracturing over n falls will therefore be given by $1 - (1 - P)^n$, which is how ARFO was defined.

As we already stated in one of our previous answers, we agree with you that this step was not actually strictly necessary at this stage for BBCT-hip. Thus, we modified the definition of ARFO to remove the dependency on n . Because BBCT-hip with ARFO only aims to predict an absolute risk of fracture when falling at the time of the CT scan, the term P used in the equation which defines ARFO would have been sufficient. We remind here that P actually represents a risk of fracture, obtained as ratio the number of falls that cause fracture and the total number of falls.

3.9. Please clarify which of the provided references are relevant for the code implementation and verification as actually performed by the vendors (Ansys) OR alternatively provide the code and describe the verification steps as actually implemented by the vendor

Applicant's position

BBCT-hip methodology outputs ARF0 combining two different models: 1) a QCT-informed patient-specific Finite Element (FE) model and 2) a mathematical stochastic model which, by randomly sampling from the probability distribution functions of a number of input parameters, calculates an impact force at the femur.

The FE model is solved using Ansys Inc Mechanical APDL software. Ansys Mechanical APDL computer program is a large-scale multipurpose commercial FE program which may be used for solving several classes of engineering analyses. The analysis capabilities of Mechanical APDL include the ability to solve static and dynamic structural analyses, steady-state and transient heat transfer problems, mode-frequency and buckling eigenvalue problems, static or time-varying magnetic analyses, and various types of field and coupled-field applications. Given a specific FE model given as input, with material properties, boundary conditions and loads defined, the software solves the FE model and computes displacements, deformation, and any other variable of interest locally. The user employs specific commandsⁱ to build the whole model (e.g. define local reference system, assign material properties, apply loads and boundary conditions, etc), and to set up the simulation. The source code and numerical algorithms to calculate the solution are then developed and implemented by APDL off-the-shelf software based on the FE theory. Hence, code verification must be carried out on the APDL solution. The Mechanical APDL (ANSYS) program has been in commercial use since 1970, and has been used extensively in the aerospace, automotive, construction, electronic, energy services, manufacturing, nuclear, plastics, oil, and steel industries. In addition, many consulting firms and hundreds of universities use Mechanical APDL for analysis, research, and educational use. Mechanical APDL is recognized worldwide as one of the most widely used and capable programs of its type.

The Mechanical APDL program is continuously being verified by the developers (ANSYS, Inc.) as new capabilities are added. The verification of the Mechanical APDL program is conducted in accordance with written procedures that form a part of an overall Quality Assurance program at ANSYS, Inc. Product development, testing, maintenance, and support processes also meet the United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission's quality requirements (10CFR50 Appendix B, 10CFR21 & NQA-1), as they have for nearly four decades. ANSYS, Inc.'s Quality System was in fact developed and evolved to meet all requirements of the nuclear industry and later enhanced to meet ISO 9001 requirements ANSYS Quality System is applicable to all ANSYS software products and services.

An Ansys Mechanical APDL verification manualⁱⁱ is available, which represents a subset of the Quality Assurance test case library which is used in full when testing new versions of Mechanical APDL. This test library and the test cases in this manual represent comparisons of Mechanical APDL solutions with known theoretical solutions, experimental results, or other independently calculated solutions. Two provided test cases (VM211 and VM184 in the Verification Manual) were used to compare the obtained numerical solution. The former one implemented the contact elements used in BBCT-hip FE model in a static analysis. Test case VM184 instead modelled a loaded straight Cantilever Beam using tetrahedral solid elements. The solution was compared to the corresponding analytical solution. The results obtained coincided with those contained in the Verification Manual. If Verification Testing tests run on the customer's installation the same as they did at ANSYS Inc.'s, it is reasoned that all tests would give results same as ANSYS, Inc.'s testingⁱⁱⁱ.

Matlab is a programming and numeric computing platform, which was used as a calculator to solve simple equations (those presented in Annex 1, where the mathematical stochastic model was explained in detail).

ⁱ ANSYS, ANSYS Command Reference Manual. 2019, ANSYS, Inc., Release 19.3

ⁱⁱ ANSYS, ANSYS Verification Manual. 2019, ANSYS, Inc., Release 19.3.

ⁱⁱⁱ ASME 2013 Verification and Validation Symposium May 24th, 2013

MathWorks has been in business for over 30 years, and its products are used in a variety of industries and safety critical applications. There are over a million users worldwide.

Software written in MATLAB has been validated by many medical device and pharmaceutical users as part of their compliance process. There are also detailed audit reports from a third-party independent testing body, TÜV SÜD in Germany. These are provided with the IEC Certification Kit regarding tool certification requirements of IEC 61508 standard and attest that the software development and validation practices followed by MathWorks adhere to the highest standards in the industry. MathWorks suggest using such documents, in conjunction with the specific tool validation reports, as part of the software tool validation documents in e.g. FDA submission.

3.10. Please clarify whether the sensitivity analyses as described in the section related to discretization errors were only performed separately or whether a global sensitivity analysis was also performed

Applicant's position

Reading your comment, we realised that in Annex 2 we erroneously called sensitivity analyses what actually are convergence analyses, which are one independent from the other, and thus need to be tested separately. We apologise for the error. Here below we provide a more detailed explanation.

The BBCT simulator is based, on one hand, on a stochastic mathematical model where a Latin Hypercube sampler executes for selected input values a fall dynamics model that predicts the impact force, and on the other on a FE model that predicts the femoral strength for a given impact direction (impact pose). For each predicted impact force, femoral fracture is predicted if the impact force is greater than the strength.

More in detail, the FE model is run 28 times, each with a different femur impact pose to estimate the femoral strength for different impact poses. In order to get the femoral strength for any possible impact force, a response surface (a surrogate model) is built based on the FE-based 28 femoral strengths, that provides the femoral strength as a function of the impact direction (ab-adduction and intra-extra rotation of the femur).

Each of the convergence analyses presented in Annex 2 aimed to quantify a particular discretisation error; we apologise if we erroneously called these sensitivity analyses; they are in fact convergence analyses aimed at estimating the upper boundary of each discretisation error. As such each analysis must be done separately, a global analysis would not make sense.

The Latin Hypercube-based ARF0 estimation converge asymptotically to the true estimates of mean and variance as the number of samples increases. We conducted a convergence analysis to estimate the upper boundary of the error due to the finite number of samples.

The reduced-order (surrogate) model that estimates the femoral strength as a function of the impact direction converges asymptotically to the true value (which in this case is the value predicted by the full-order FE model) as the number of samples increases. We conducted a convergence analysis to estimate the upper boundary of the error due to the finite number of samples.

The analysis of the mesh refinement is part of the verification (quantification of the approximation errors, due to the numerical solution of equations) of the Finite Element model; it is not a sensitivity analysis (which aims to quantify the aleatoric error, how the uncertainty affecting the model's inputs propagate into the model's outputs), but a convergence analysis aimed to provide an upper boundary estimation of approximation error due to the spatial discretisation.

In the mathematical model that predicts the deformation of the femur under loading, the elastic properties of the bone are assumed as heterogenous over space. This implies a continuum representation, but also in this case the finite element solution provides only a spatially discrete description of the bone tissue elasticity, which converges to the exact distribution as the number of individual elasticity values increases. This convergence analysis aims to provide an upper boundary estimation of the approximation error due to the discretisation of the otherwise continuous elastic properties.

3.11. Please discuss the link between the initial and final inclination angles (θ_i and θ_f) in the computation of the impact forces F and the impact directions simulated with the finite element model. Explain how the link between these entities was taken into account or (alternatively) the impact of not taking this into account

Applicant's position

As we have already mentioned, BBCT-hip is composed of two distinct parts: 1) a mathematical stochastic model which predicts 1 million possible impact forces at the femur and 2) a QCT-informed finite element femur model which computes the strength of the femur (i.e. its load to failure) in 28 different femoral impact poses. These resulting 28 strength values are then used to inform a response surface (a surrogate model) which by linear interpolation calculates the strength along any intermediate orientation.

We here highlight that in the context of the mathematical stochastic model we define with θ_i and θ_f the initial and final inclinations of the body with respect to the vertical, as shown in Fig. 3.11.1 below.

Figure 3.11.1 θ_i and θ_f angles as used in the mathematical model used to compute the impact force due to a fall.

θ_i can range between zero (which means the fall initiate from the standing position), and $\hat{\theta}_i$, which is the maximum inclination beyond which the fall would initiate even in static conditions. θ_f is normally 90° , which correspond to an impact to a flat floor. Values greater than 90° imply one is falling from an elevation, such as a stair step; values lower than 90° imply one is falling on a slope. Because a fall can initiate and terminate in a number of ways, θ_i and θ_f cannot be deterministic and therefore are treated as stochastic variables (see reply to issue 3.7).

The final inclination of the body with respect to the vertical is not correlated to the pose the femur has at impact (defined by the intra-extra rotation angle α and add-abduction angle β) (Fig. 3.11.2).

Figure 3.11.2 Angles α and β as defined with respect the femur anatomical reference system.

The initial and final body inclinations with respect to the vertical affect the velocity at the impact and therefore the impact force definition. Nevertheless, they cannot be directly related to how the femur will be oriented at the impact (femoral impact pose). Hence, the femoral strength along the full range of possible orientations the femur might impact the ground along (ab-adduction and intra-extra rotation) is explored.

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3.12. It is stated that a sensitivity to estimate the effect of the number N of simulated falls on ARF0 computation was judged of interest. For N=106, ARF0 can be determined to a numerical precision better than 2%. It is unclear how this was determined. Please clarify

Applicant's position

We are sorry to have erroneously called such analysis a sensitivity analysis, since that was actually a convergence analysis, as stated previously. Basically, starting from 10² fall impact forces predicted by the stochastic mathematical model we incremented that number by one order of magnitude progressively until 10⁷. Each time the patient specific ARF0 was calculated, and the difference calculated with respect to the ARF0 values as computed considering the largest number of falls within the model (i.e. 10⁷).

Below, such difference is reported as a function of the number of falls considered.

Figure 3.12.1 Convergence analysis on the number of impact forces employed to estimate ARF0. Three patients are shown, identified as those characterized by the highest, lowest and closest to the median ARF0 values.

3.13. In the sensitivity analysis performed to assess the effect of the impact directions simulated with the full-order finite element model to inform the reduced-order model on ARF0, it seems like only one scenario was tested. There is a need for explanation on how this will be expanded to the whole range of scenarios (and with all the possible QCT scan values)

Applicant's position

As already mentioned, we are sorry to have erroneously defined as sensitivity analyses what in reality are convergence analyses. In this case we aimed to assess the error caused by replacing the finite element model with a surrogate model (response surface) as a function of the number of simulations used to generate the response surface, each corresponding to a different femoral impact pose.

In Annex 2 of the submitted Briefing Book we presented the results obtained for one single patient comparing the ARF0 values resulting from a surrogate model developed based on 28 (10° intervals for α and β angles range) and 91 (5° intervals for α and β angles range) full-order finite element models. We agree that such convergence analysis was limited in the scenarios explored. The reviewers are correct in noticing that this study was done for a single subject. While femoral anatomy is similar between subjects, in theory different local curvatures of the femur could cause the error due to the response surface to converge as the number of samples increase with different rates in different subjects. Thus, we have planned to extend this verification study to include enough subjects to ensure the average sampling error across subjects converges.

We have carried out ARF0 calculations for 100 patients based on surrogate models built from 28 (10° intervals for α and β angles range), 91 (5° intervals for α and β angles range) and 496 (2° intervals for α and β angles range) full-order FE simulations. The percentage difference between the ARF0 obtained from the two 'coarser' surrogate models (10° and 5° sampling) and those computed based on the 'finest' (2° sampling) was computed. It was found to be 2.04% and 0.66% for the 10° and 5° sampling-based surrogate models respectively.

3.14. Details on how the Applicant intends to link the output from the BBCT-hip to the number of observed events are missing from the BP and should be provided

Applicant's position

The primary outcome metrics are hip fracture events. On the other hand, BBCT-hip predicts ARF0, the absolute risk of hip fracture that a subject at the time of the CT scan faces upon falling. When ARF0 is used as response variable to select the optimal dose, we assume that the change in ARF0 between the beginning and the end of the treatment period is a valid measure of the response to treatment. If this is the case the response variable must be a valid proxy for efficacy, measured in this case as reduction of the number of hip fracture events over a given time (say 5 years).

If BBCT-hip could predict ARF5 (the absolute risk of hip fracture that a subject faces upon falling in the five years after the CT scan) the link to the primary outcome would be more evident. The reduction of the number of hip fracture events over a given time that a treatment causes if compared to placebo (or to a known comparator) is due to the reduced biomechanical strength of the femur caused by the progression of the disease (without proper treatment), to the patient's propensity to fall, and to the patient's major or minor ability to attenuate the intensity of the impact upon falling. Given the effect of the drug is limited to the first determinant, Randomized Clinical Trials (RCT) are usually designed to make sure that the two treatment arms present comparable frequency of falling and general neuromotor condition. If this is true, we can assume the difference between the two treatment arms is only due to the change in biomechanical strength due to disease progression and treatment effect. In this context, the difference in ARF5 between the two treatment arms (assuming the BBCT-hip methodology is valid) should be strongly correlated with the change in the number of hip fractures observed between the two treatment arms.

We acknowledge that the relationship with ARF0 is less obvious. In the clinical validation study, we proposed in Design #2 (see reply to issue 3.4) to test the validity of this response variable by testing the correlation of the change of ARF0 after one year of treatment (Δ ARF0) with the rate of hip fracture in the following 5 years. The difference of Δ ARF0 between the two treatment arms is correlated to the difference in hip fracture rate if the change of the risk of fracture during the time of observation (say 5 years) is small. In other word, if we can assume that ARF0 is close in value to ARF5, it can be assumed as an estimate of ARF5. Osteoporosis is usually a slow-progressing disease, so such assumption seems plausible. But more important, when we assume Δ ARF0 as a predictor of the change in hip fracture rate, any eventual progression of the disease over the observation time would reduce the correlation of difference of ARF0 with change in fracture rate. Thus, by measuring the correlation of Δ ARF0 with the fracture rate over 5 years, we would test the validity of the assumption that ARF0 is a valid response variable.

3.15. The supporting clinical data for the validation strategy have different follow-up times, i.e. 90 days in the first case and 5 yrs in the second case. At the moment it is unclear how the BBTC-hip predictions are to be interpreted in the context of varying follow-up times. Please clarify

Applicant's position

As we explained in our reply to issue n. 3.14, our long-term goal is to develop a time-dependent predictor, which confirms that we agree that follow-up time matters; we apologise if we gave the impression to state the opposite. Again, as explained in reply n. 3.14, what we assume is that since the risk of hip fracture changes slowly over time, ARFO can still be a good predictor of the risk of fracture at 5 years. To the purpose, in the revised clinical validation study, we propose to evaluate longitudinal validity by assessing the correlation of the ARFO risk with the time to fracture in those who fracture within the five years. The error we commit in neglecting that in the five years the risk of fracture of an untreated patient is likely to increase will weaken such correlation. If that is still significant, this should confirm the validity of our assumption.

3.16. In the clinical data used in the technical validation the Applicant derived a ARF0 threshold of 0.374 that showed, according to the Applicant, good sensitivity and specificity for predicting hip fractures. This threshold is a component of the model and should be validated. In other words, prior to the clinical validation study this threshold should be fixed. Of note finding the best threshold for predicting hip fractures should be considered part of model building and cannot be part of the validation strategy. Please discuss the plans to this regard

Applicant's position

We agree with this observation. The clinical validation plan should be based on a threshold for classification determined a priori and not identified using the same subjects enrolled for the clinical validation.

The ARF0 threshold you refer to was identified on the Sheffield retrospective cohort, used in the technical validation. In that case we were more interested in comparing the overall AUC value with respect to other possible response variable, such as aBMD or FRAX.

We believe that the threshold value is reliable. Because of the high percentage of fractured patients in the Sheffield cohort, the statistical power is sufficient in spite of the relatively small size of the cohort. To confirm this, we have performed a 10-fold cross-validation on it. Ten different ROC analyses were performed, each time leaving out a subset of the original cohort. The coefficient of variation computed on the 10 resulting threshold values settled at 2.4%.

However, the revised clinical validation plan does not require a threshold for classification.

3.17. A sample size of 100, with 5 expected cases is inappropriate and any comparison based on this will be underpowered. Please clarify how it was possible to construct a meaningful ROC curve based on such sparse events

Applicant's position

As already written in the reply to issue 3.4 we accept the criticism on the design and the sample size of the clinical validation study we proposed. In the reply to issue n. 3.4 we suggested two possible alternative designs. In the design #1 the numerosity of the study will be calculated a priori, powering the study for the expected change in aBMD between two widely used treatments, using the abundant information available in the literature.

Such information is not available for ARF0. Thus, in Design #2, where we power the study for the change in ARF0, we will need to use an adaptive study design. We would initially enrol 50 patients for each dose group; we will then decompose the distribution of Δ ARF0 for the whole 100 patient, which we expect to be bimodal. We will then split such bimodal distribution in two monomodal distributions and calculate the sample size powering the probability that the two monomodal distributions are different.

3.18. Please provide the explicit mathematical expression of the link between F and P in complement to equation 9 in the annex 1 document

Applicant's position

The impact force is affected by some deterministic quantities and some stochastic variables. Using a Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) of the frequency distribution of each variable, assumed to be independent from the others (so no covariance) we generate one million predictions of possible impact forces. Using the same LHS, we also sample the probability distribution that at the time of impact the femur has a certain intra-extra rotation, and ab-adduction (pose of impact), values that affect the force requires to fracture the femur (femoral strength).

For each of the one million impact forces, we compare such force to the force required to fracture the femur in the given pose of impact (femoral strength). P is merely the number of simulated falls for which the model predicts fracture, divided by the total number of simulated falls.

Mathematically, $n = 1, \dots, N$ is the fall number, i.e. one of N total number of simulated falls. $I(n)$ is the force that impact transmits to the femur for fall n . F is the force required to fracture the femur, which varies as a function of the femoral orientations, α and β . We assume a fall cause fracture if $I(n) > F$. N_F is the number of simulated falls that cause fracture. $P = \frac{N_F}{N}$ is the absolute risk of fracture.

4. References

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